

Fighting for gender equality in research & science: What works?

Lessons learned from the MINDtheGEPs project

Achieving gender equality in research and science is a long-term, systemic process. It requires reliable data, strong leadership, and the combined use of top-down and bottom-up approaches. It also depends on the active involvement of management and decision-makers, collaboration with gender experts, a reflexive and participatory approach to opening up dialogue across disciplines, genders, and career levels, and alignment with national and institutional contexts.

Drawing from MINDtheGEPs experience, this policy brief offers a roadmap for organisations to make their gender equality efforts last, ensuring that they strengthen both wellbeing and research excellence producing "happier" organisations and researchers.

Key implications for stakeholders

For the European Commission

- > Maintain Gender Equality Plans as a core eligibility criterion for EU research funding.
- > Ensure that governance structures, training, and structural reforms are fully eligible costs in funding programmes.
- > Strengthen cross-national learning and peer monitoring through dedicated projects and mutual learning mechanisms.

For the Scientific Community

- > Treat diversity and care work as integral to research excellence, not as secondary activities.
- > Share evidence, tools, and good practices on gender equality systematically.
- > Critically challenge biased ideas of merit and productivity, especially the notions of **neutral merit** and the **unconditional worker**.

For Research Performing Organisations

- > Integrate gender equality in recruitment, promotion, evaluation, and workload systems.
- > Establish formal governance structures and fund gender equality roles.
- > Commit to continuous monitoring, self-reflection and reporting.

MINDtheGEPs supported the design and implementation of Gender Equality Plans across 5 countries and 7 research-performing organisations from 2021 to 2025. The project used a feminist framework, guided by standpoint theory and intersectional approaches, conceptualising gender as a social structure. Through participatory training and self-reflection initiatives (within and across organisations), data-driven strategies, and the establishment of dedicated governance structures, the project promoted inclusive and sustainable approaches to gender equality.

MINDtheGEPs shows that achieving structural transformation requires more than policy instruments – it demands cultural shifts, organisational commitment, resources, and an integrated, participatory process to breaking down resistance and build consensus around the why and how of gender inequalities.

This policy brief was written for research performing organisations, the European Commission & the scientific community.

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Key lessons learned from 4,5 years of MINDtheGEPs

Fixing the system – not the women

Traditional approaches to gender inequality often focus on increasing the number of women in specific positions in an organisation. MINDtheGEPs shows this is insufficient, if you are not also changing the system, which means not only fixing numbers, but also knowledge and institutions.

- Challenge the **publish-or-perish** model and the ideal of the **unconditional worker**.
- Rethink evaluation criteria, recruitment, and promotion systems.
- Redistribute academic labour, recognising caregiving and organisational tasks.
- Do not reward overwork & unsustainable productivity, but establish career paths and forms of doing science more **collaborative**, interdisciplinary and **slower**.

No data? No policy

Gender is a social structure shaped by multiple, intersecting barriers. Effective action depends on **evidence from different levels and methods**:

- **Macro level:** Mapping the national context for gender equality, including overall and sector-specific gender equality levels (based on the EIGE Gender Equality Index), research and higher education investments and policies, laws supporting gender equality and Gender Equality Plans, and labour market and social policies that support work-life balance and **shared caregiving between women and men**.
- **Meso level:** Following the approach of **gender budgeting** and **gender auditing** to measure gender equality indicators within an organisation, including the share of women in governance and at different career levels across disciplines (the so-called **gender scissors**), access to funding, and the presence of gender equality policies and measures.
- **Micro level:** Use surveys and interviews to capture **opinions** and **lived experiences** of people directly involved in research, making sure to include researchers at different career stages, in different disciplines, alongside key informants that hold or have held important positions in the organisation.

Mixed-method approaches, **quantitative and qualitative**, are essential for designing tailored, relevant, and sustainable Gender Equality Plans.

Governance

Sustaining gender equality work requires a wide range of skills, continuous effort, time, and financial resources. It calls for a strategically positioned coordinator (such as a **gender officer**) with dedicated funding and time. But that is not enough. Functional and recognised governance structures, with both scientific and managerial/administrative competencies, are essential for effective design and implementation of intersecting measures that enable real structural change. In MINDtheGEPs, partners established several governance structures with clearly defined mandates, roles, and responsibilities. These include a *Gender Equality Team*, a *Gender Equality Plan Implementing Board*, a *Gender Equality Manager*, a *Gender Data Manager*, a *Rector's Delegate for Equality*, and a *Delegates Network*: a network of representatives from various departments.

Monitoring & evaluation

Real change requires continuous monitoring and self-evaluation. This involves regularly assessing both the results of actions (using clear indicators) and the change process itself (how resistance is addressed, alliances are built, and responsibilities shared). Monitoring should be an ongoing, participatory process within and across organisations, supporting & encouraging reflection, problem-solving, and timely adjustments.

Evaluation should focus on:

- **Effectiveness:** Did the action meet its goal?
- **Relevance:** Is it meaningful and contextually appropriate?
- **Impact:** Are results measurable and shared?
- **Sustainability:** Will outcomes last?

The 4 pillars of sustainable change are:

1. **Creating a transformational agent:** an internal team progressively develops the capacity to lead and manage institutional change through a gender action plan.
2. **Activating agency dynamics:** The implementation of the plan mobilises engagement, manages resistance, and builds support for change. The interaction between agency and organisational structures, including norms, resources, and context.
3. **Interaction with structural conditions:** the team's change efforts interact with organisational structures that can enable or constrain achievable outcomes.
4. **Sustaining institutional outcomes:** the process aims to produce lasting organisational and cultural change that continues to advance gender equality over time.

A pendulum approach between culture & structure

Gender inequality shapes what counts as knowledge, whose problems are studied, and how **excellence** is defined – influencing research agendas, funding, and curricula. Care work and work-life balance are essential to both individual and organisational wellbeing, yet undervalued and largely borne by women. As a result, the precarious contracts, short-term funding, and mobility demands of academia continue to disadvantage women and other marginalised groups.

Structural measures like extra research funding and teaching leave after maternity, or targeted career support are vital but insufficient without a cultural shift that challenges **gendered care roles** and the **publish-or-perish** culture that fuels overwork and inequality. Promoting women to leadership and diversifying decision-making must go hand in hand with creating spaces for reflection that question biased ideas of excellence and of **neutral networks** and recognise how **employment insecurity** undermines both wellbeing and innovation.

The success of gender equality measures depends on engaging governance bodies and researchers of all genders and for every discipline, at every career stage – including those who may feel either advantaged or disadvantaged by such policies. Evidence of gender imbalances should be shared widely, their structural causes discussed, and good practices exchanged. Feminist scholars play a vital role in training, reflection, and decision-making, helping to uncover inequalities and challenge superficial approaches such as **pinkwashing** – adopting the language of equality without real change. Equally important is the active **involvement of men**, who continue to dominate decision-making spaces yet often overlook or individualise systemic gender processes.

Changing culture

Cultural change requires spaces for reflection and dialogue that challenge male-dominated leadership models and myths of meritocracy; address the persistent link between women and unpaid care work; recognise care as valuable for institutions and society; and recognise science and excellence as a collective, inclusive, and ethical enterprise. MINDtheGEPs adopted a capacity-building, **train-the-trainers approach** that equipped selected staff with the skills and tools needed to conduct training and create spaces for reflection and negotiations on gender equality.

A core group (often gender officers, HR professionals, and committed researchers) at partner organisations were trained to act as multipliers, fostering internal ownership and sustainable cultural change from within the organisation. To ensure open, non-hierarchical dialogue, two types of workshops were organised: early-career sessions to empower young researchers, and senior sessions to engage decision-makers in reflection and commitment.

Changing structure

Cultural actions are more likely to bring about real change when combined with structural measures that redistribute workloads and diversify committees; address the motherhood penalty by reducing the teaching loads and providing additional funds for women following their maternity leave; emphasise the importance of increasing fathers' involvement to reach a **dual earner-dual carer** society and against the **unconditional worker model** for all; and use **positive actions** (e.g. incentives for promoting women to tenured positions or to full professorships or gender quotas in decision-making bodies) to open the glass door and break the glass ceiling.

Conclusions

- > Sustainable gender equality requires systemic reform, not individual adaptation – the system needs fixing, not the women.
- > Evidence should be the driver: without multitypes of reliable data, there will be no effective policy.
- > Structural and cultural change must go hand in hand; one without the other is insufficient.
- > Strong governance and continuous monitoring are essential for long-term sustainability.
- > Change must combine top-down leadership with bottom-up engagement, involving both decision-makers and researchers at all career stages and across genders & disciplines to ensure continuity even when institutional support weakens.
- > Men must become allies and advocates for gender equality in both discourse(s) and practice(s).
- > By institutionalising these principles, research organisations, the European Commission, and the scientific community can build fairer and "happier" workplaces, enhance research quality, and strengthen Europe's innovation capacity.

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MINDtheGEPs gender equality in research

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